

OBJECTIVE FEATURES OF HOOLIGANISM COMMITTED BY A GROUP OF INDIVIDUALS**A.A.Qabulov,****“Independent researcher at the University of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan.**

This article analyzes the objective features of hooliganism committed by a group of individuals. The actions committed, their social danger, and methods of execution are considered as objective features. The specific characteristics of hooliganism carried out by a group are also discussed.

Keywords: Hooliganism, group commission, objective features, legal analysis, social danger.

According to criminologists, hooliganism is considered the “starting school” of criminal behavior, especially for crimes involving violence or malicious intent.

The statistics on these crimes demonstrate their “spread.” In 2019, 953 hooliganism crimes were committed; in 2020, 1,448; in 2021, 2,717; in 2022, 3,129; and in the first nine months of 2023, 2,393¹. Naturally, considering that this statistic does not reflect other crimes or administrative offenses resulting from hooliganism, the actual scope is even larger.

An analysis of the statistics from the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan indicates that although hooliganism is not a major category of crime, its

¹Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди сайти маълумотлари.// <https://stat.sud.uz>

consequences, such as harm to citizens' lives, health, or property, and its high social danger, are evident.

From 2019 to 2023, the number of people convicted for hooliganism has steadily increased. Moreover, crimes such as bodily harm and torture are often closely linked to hooliganism and also show an upward trend. Furthermore, the number of people exempted from liability for various reasons in cases involving fights, minor bodily harm, and other related crimes is also significant.

These findings suggest that the actual extent of hooliganism is much higher than what is reflected in official data.

Criminology methods of study help answer complex questions in criminal law, such as what measures should be applied to prevent crimes from occurring¹. It is important to emphasize that law enforcement agencies are more likely to achieve the desired outcomes in preventing hooliganism when they rely on scientifically grounded methods².

The object of hooliganism is a necessary objective feature. Based on the generally accepted classification of

¹Кудрявцев В.Н. Причинность в криминологии (о структуре индивидуального преступного поведения). Монография. М.: ТК Велби, Из-во Проспект, 2007. С. 4.

²Кудрявцев В.Н., Эминов В.Е. Причины преступности в России: Криминологический анализ. М.: Норма, 2006. С. 23.

objects in vertical and horizontal directions, we identify the general, similar, and direct objects of hooliganism.

When discussing the importance of identifying the object of hooliganism in criminal law theory and its practical application, I.Ya. Kozachenko points out that completing this task not only reveals the social-legal essence of hooliganism but also allows for determining its level of social danger. Therefore, to achieve the goals of this study, it is necessary to identify the general, similar, and direct objects of hooliganism.

Various perspectives are presented in the literature regarding this issue: according to Article 277 of the Criminal Code, the general object of hooliganism is public safety and public order.

Article 277 is located in the Special Part of the Criminal Code under the section “Crimes Against Public Safety and Public Order,” so the general object of hooliganism must be public safety and public order.

When analyzing the general and similar objects of hooliganism, it is important to note that some neighboring countries, such as Armenia, Belarus, and Tajikistan, include social morality rules in addition to public order in this section. Scholars like V.S. Komissarov and V.I. Zarubin support the use of foreign practice in this regard.

Apparently, in their view, public morality and etiquette are inseparable elements of public order and public safety, and they believe that these elements are not singled out as independent objects of criminal-legal protection in Article 2, Part 1 of the Criminal Code.

The issue of identifying the direct object of hooliganism is also highly debated. Based on the disposition of Article 277 of the Criminal Code, hooliganism is defined as deliberate disrespect for the rules of public conduct, fighting, minor bodily harm, or damage or destruction of someone else’s property.

This suggests that the direct object of hooliganism is public order.

According to the current wording of Article 277, hooliganism encroaches on several direct objects. The first is social relations that ensure public order. The second object is considered an alternative because hooliganism occurs when at least one of the following social relations is violated: health, bodily integrity; property rights (but not in opposition to the distribution of material goods, as this would fall under crimes such as robbery)¹.

Thus, we can conclude that the main direct object of

¹Овчаренко Е.И. Правовая характеристика хулиганства // Журнал российского права. 2004. №3. С.43.

hooliganism is public order. Several scholars, such as T.Z. B. Volzhenkin¹, Apostolova², N.A. Egorova³, V.V. Maltsev⁴, V. Veklenko, and E. Zaitseva⁵, point out in the current wording of this article that hooliganism, as a violent crime, may involve the use of cold weapons or items that can harm a person's health (weapons). Therefore, they also include human health as an object of hooliganism.

The concept of public order as an object of hooliganism has caused significant debate in criminal law theory. For instance, V.I. Zarubin and A.V. Ragulin consider public order as a set of social relations regulated by legal and moral norms. Similarly, S.S. Yatsenko, V.N. Radchenko, A.S. Mikhlin, V.V. Kazakova, V.M. Lebedev, F.E. Kolontaevsky, G.N. Borzenkov, V.S. Komissarov, A.V. Naumov, and A.I. Chuchaev support this view.

At the same time, A.A. Chekalin, V.T. Tomin, and V.V. Sverchkov define public order as "a system of moral and ethical standards, legal norms, and other social norms that regulate human behavior and relationships." This view is also supported by E.G. Lipatov and S.E. Chanov.

¹Волженкин Б. Хулиганство // Уголовное право. 2007. №5. С. 17-22.

²Апостолова Ц.З. Дискуссионные аспекты уголовно-правовой характеристики хулиганства в редакции федерального закона от 24 июля 2007 года №211 - ФЗ // Российский следователь. 2007. №24. С.11.

³Егорова Н.А. Новое постановление Пленума Верховного Суда РФ о хулиганстве и иных преступлениях, совершенных из хулиганских побуждений (вопросы и решения) // Мировой судья. 2008. №6. С.26-29.

⁴Мальцев В.В. Квалификация хулиганства // Следователь. 2004. №10. С.3-4.

⁵Векленко В., Зайцева Е. Спорные вопросы квалификации преступлений, совершенных с применением оружия или предметов, используемых в качестве оружия // Уголовное право. - М.: АНО "Юридические программы", 2009, № 2. - С. 23-29

T.M. Kafarov and Ch.T. Musaev see public order as the necessary condition for citizens' normal life, including normal social, political, economic, and leisure activities¹.

The specific original definition of "public order" was proposed by N. Ivanov, who argued that public order is nothing other than "the range of actions permitted by society."²

In conclusion, it can be seen that there is no universally accepted interpretation of the concept of "public order" in criminal law theory. However, when identifying the concept in this study, we can summarize the most common features of public order: it is a system of social relations regulated by legal and non-legal norms; it ensures the well-being and coexistence of individuals; and it is based on moral and ethical principles.

Thus, public order is a system of social relations that is historically formed, dictated by the interests of society and individuals, and regulated by moral ideals, legal norms, and other social norms. It protects the life and health of individuals, ensures respect for their dignity and rights, provides the conditions necessary for the normal functioning of individuals and institutions, and guarantees peace and public safety.

¹ Кафаров Т.М., Мусаев Ч.Т. Борьба с посягательством на общественный порядок. Баку, 1983. С.23.

²Иванов Н. Хулиганство: проблемы квалификации. // Российская юстиция. 1996.№8. С.39.

By summarizing the above, we can conclude that the general and similar object of hooliganism is public order, which is historically shaped, required by the interests of society and individuals, and regulated by ethical, legal, and social norms. It ensures the protection of individual life and health, respects human dignity and public morality, creates conditions for peaceful coexistence, and ensures public peace, the protection of all types of property, leisure, and normal functioning for individuals and institutions.

The concept of "public order" consists of two words: "society" and "order." The first refers to a community of people living together and interacting based on historically formed systems. Order is the correct, established condition or arrangement of something, as well as the method of its organization. Therefore, in the broadest sense, public order can be defined as the normal state of a community of people, which is shaped by the social forms of collective living and activity. This

definition can be adjusted depending on various factors, primarily the social-political structure of a particular state during a given period.

T.M. Kaferov and Ch.T. Musaev define public order as the socially accepted activities of state institutions, enterprises, public organizations, as well as normal social-political, productive, and other activities, which are necessary for ensuring the normal life and rest of citizens¹. Similar definitions are also found in the works of other scholars from the Soviet era.

A.P. Korenev describes public order as a system of social relations, secured by legal norms, ethics, and public rules, which establishes rights and obligations to protect the life, inviolability, honor, dignity, and other rights of participants in these relations, as well as public and private property, ensuring public order in public places, and providing the necessary conditions for the normal functioning of organizations, enterprises, and officials².

Currently, there is no single, universally accepted definition of "public order." However, the definitions proposed by various researchers are quite general and encompass a wide range of elements³.

N. G. Ivanov believes that public order is inevitably violated whenever a criminal act is committed, and therefore, public order cannot be directly considered as the object of petty hooliganism. In our view, this position is debatable. Specifically, in crimes against individuals, the object directly violated is the protection of the victim, and public order is violated as a result of and to the extent corresponding to the violation of these relations.

¹ Кафаров Т.М., Мусаев Ч.Т. Борьба с посягательством на общественный порядок. Баку, 1983. С. 23.

²Административная деятельность ОВД / Под ред. А.П. Коренева. М., 2009. С. 23.

³Иванов Н. Хулиганство: проблемы квалификации // Российская юстиция. 1996. № 8. С. 39-41.

Conversely, when a criminal commits hooliganism, they directly attempt to violate public order, undermining the social relations system established by legal norms, customs, traditions, and moral standards. This includes actions that disrupt public peace, hinder normal working and resting conditions, and disrupt the daily life of citizens, as well as the functioning of organizations, enterprises, and institutions.

Based on the above, we conclude that public order, as an object of hooliganism, should be understood as a system of social relations aimed at ensuring public peace, normal working conditions, citizens' right to rest and live peacefully, and the functioning of institutions, enterprises,

and organizations, as defined by current legal norms, customs, traditions, and moral standards. In our opinion, this definition best meets modern requirements.

From this, we can also infer that:

The general object of petty hooliganism is public safety.

The related object is public order.

The direct object (at the necessary object level) is the specific state of public order violated by the actions of the perpetrator.

At the same time, the analysis of previous scientific studies shows that there is no consensus in the academic field regarding the alternative direct object of hooliganism.

For instance, E.G. Smirnova argues that the additional direct object of hooliganism consists of social relations in the field of protecting an individual's health. Also, the social relations in the field of state governance and maintaining order are highlighted as an alternative direct object of hooliganism¹.

We believe that this position requires clarification. Specifically, Article 277 of the Criminal Code includes social relations concerning the protection of human health, as well as those ensuring the protection of state, public, and private property as additional or alternative objects.

It is important to note that the characteristic feature of the object of hooliganism is the necessary and organic connection between the main and additional objects of criminal attacks. Therefore, if the personal rights indicated in the disposition of Article 277 of the Criminal Code are violated, but the main object (public order) is not violated, hooliganism would not be considered as part of the crime. Thus, it would be more appropriate to

¹ Смирнова Е.Г. Хулиганство: Уголовно-правовые и криминологические аспекты: Автореф. дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. Краснодар, 2005. С. 21.

view the violation of human health or property as an additional but necessary object of hooliganism.

It is also important to emphasize that including clause "v" of part 3 of Article 277 in the current version raises numerous problematic questions for law enforcement officers, particularly regarding the identification of the object of the criminal offense. Specifically, a logical question arises within the context of considering the object of hooliganism: Can the foundations of the constitutional system and/or state security be considered as alternative additional objects of hooliganism?

The current version of Article 277 of the Criminal Code implies that constitutional system foundations and state security can be included as an alternative additional object because

hooliganism committed by a group of individuals during public events could be based on political, ideological, racial, ethnic, or religious hostility, or animosity towards any social group¹. Therefore, actions that incite hatred or animosity against individuals or groups based on their race, ethnicity, language, origin, or religious beliefs, or aimed at degrading their dignity, especially during public events, logically support the inclusion of constitutional system and state security as

¹ Қаранг: Власов В.П., Лубшев Ю.Ф. Борьба с хулиганством. М.: Юрид. лит., 1972. С. 27.

alternative additional objects of this crime.

Furthermore, when hooliganism is committed by a group of people, actions are often carried out with the intent to incite racial, ethnic, or religious hostility. The legislature may, therefore, find it appropriate to emphasize that such actions constitute an attack not only on the individual but also on the societal and state foundations, particularly as Uzbekistan is a multi-ethnic nation with sovereign integrity. Any attacks on its constitution or internal stability could threaten its constitutional order and territorial integrity.

According to Part 1 of Article 277 of the Criminal Code, any person can become a victim of hooliganism. However, it should be noted that under Part 2, "d," victims of hooliganism are specifically defined as children, the elderly, persons with disabilities, or individuals in a vulnerable state.

Additionally, Part 3 of Article 277 of the Criminal Code defines a specific circle of victims:

Representatives of authority performing public order maintenance duties, including law enforcement or supervisory officials and other persons with administrative powers as per legal norms, regardless of their formal subordination.

Public representatives or other citizens involved in ensuring public order and preventing hooliganism, even if they are not state officials.

Based on the current version of Article 277 of the Criminal Code, we can state that the victim is not an optional or additional feature, but a necessary attribute of the object of hooliganism. Our study of hooliganism-related criminal cases shows that in 98% of cases, the victim is an individual. Thus, while it is possible that legal entities could also suffer damage from hooliganism, they are always represented by physical persons.

It should also be noted that the necessary additional (alternative) feature of the object of hooliganism under Article 277 of the Criminal Code is the property of others, as the disposition of this article specifies that damage or destruction of another's property during hooliganism constitutes an integral part of the offense.

The objective side of the crime is the essential feature. In criminal law theory, the objective side refers to the set of legal characteristics describing the external manifestation of socially dangerous acts¹.

At present, the generally accepted position in criminal law is that hooliganism can only be committed through

¹Уголовное право Российской Федерации. Общая часть: Учебник для вузов / Подред. А.И. Рарога, А.С. Самойлова. М.: Высшее образование, 2005. С. 143.

action. However, there is an alternative viewpoint expressed by A.A. Piontkovsky, who notes that "hooliganism can be committed through inaction, but such inaction is not as dangerous as to justify repressive legal measures¹." However, we believe that hooliganism punishable by law cannot be committed through inaction. This is confirmed by the opinions of many legal scholars and by the examination of criminal case materials, which show no instances of hooliganism being committed through inaction.

According to Part 1 of Article 277 of the Criminal Code, hooliganism involves intentional disregard for public order, fighting, bodily harm, or damage or destruction of property. However, the concept of disregard for public order is not clearly defined in criminal law. It is up to law enforcement officers to decide whether the individual's behavior constitutes a blatant violation of public order, based on visible signs of disrespect toward society.

Currently, the Supreme Court of Uzbekistan, in its Plenary Decision of June 14, 2002 (Resolution No. 9), defines "intentional disregard for public order" as the blatant violation of public order established by legal norms, customs, and ethical standards².

¹Пионтковский А.А., Меньшагин В.Д., Чхиквадзе В.М. Курс советского уголовного права. Особенная часть. М.: Госюриздат, 1959. Т. 2. С. 509;

²Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленумининг 2002 йил 14 июндаги 9-сонли "Безориликка оид ишлар бўйича суд амалиёти ҳақида"ги қарори // <https://lex.uz/docs/1452654>

Also, the concept of "indecenty" is determined by the method, time, place, and conditions under which the crime is committed. Based on Part 1 of Article 277 of the Criminal Code, hooliganism's objective side includes fighting, bodily harm, and damage to property.

Regarding the location of the crime: 39% of crimes occur in streets, boulevards, and recreation areas; 21% in markets and their surroundings; 18% in cafes, bars, tea houses, night clubs, etc.;

6.2% in enterprises, organizations, and institutions; 0.8% in transport vehicles; 8% in sports and health improvement facilities; 7% in educational institutions and student accommodations.

Article 277, Part 1 of the Criminal Code does not form the objective element of the offense of hooliganism when there is a threat of violence or the destruction or damage of property. Based on the current disposition of Part 1 of Article 277, it can be argued that more than 70% of hooliganism actions are qualified according to this part.

Only about 18-20% of crimes are qualified under Part 2 of Article 277, and only 7-10% under Part 3 of Article 277.

At the same time, it is noted in the literature that the influence of various situations on the qualification of the crime of "deliberate disrespect for public order" is not entirely clear. For example, if a group of individuals, having conspired in advance, violates public order based on political, ideological, racial, national, or religious hatred or enmity, or seeks revenge against a particular social group¹, such actions may be considered as public disorder, especially if they obstruct traffic, overturn vehicles, or cause harm to some people.

Therefore, it is of great importance to define the concept of "deliberate disrespect for public order" to correctly determine the objective side of hooliganism.

As V.N. Kudryavtsev emphasized, "It is of great importance to combine all the characteristics of the crime in legal documents when resolving the problem of criminalizing actions, as it is a necessary condition for applying the law correctly and qualifying the crime in accordance with legal documents. The rule of law undoubtedly contributes more to societal interests than lawlessness and arbitrariness."²

The disposition of Part 1 of Article 27 of the Criminal Code is manifested in the concept of "deliberate disrespect for public order." In criminal law, these features are referred to as evaluative. In particular, "the legal definitions are not aimed at reflecting the object in its entirety but at capturing the characteristics of this

¹Аистова Л.С. Хулиганство как преступление против личности // Криминалисть. СПб.: Изд-во С.-Петербур. юрид. ин-та Академии Ген. прокуратуры РФ, 2010. № 1 (6). С. 34-38.

² Российское уголовное право. Особенная часть / Под ред. В.Н. Кудрявцева и А.В. Наумова. М.: Юрист, 1997. С. 228.

object... the legal meaning of criminal concepts is determined by the person applying criminal law, taking into account the actual circumstances of the case..."¹

Evaluative concepts can be considered relatively precise, and their content is only revealed considering the specific situation and characteristics of the case at hand. Based on these definitions, it can be concluded that the interpretation of such evaluative concepts falls under the authority of law enforcement officers.

It has been repeatedly emphasized in legal literature and judicial practice that in order to determine the occurrence of "deliberate disrespect for public order," law enforcement officers must carefully analyze all the actions of the person who committed the crime¹.

It should be noted that when assessing the crime from a public morality perspective, the law enforcement officer must determine whether public moral principles were violated, considering the place and time the crime occurred, the manner of its expression, the presence of victims, the nature of the offense, and the level of social danger. These characteristics describe the degree of social danger of the crime and indicate how much it

¹ Шубин В.В. Рассмотрение уголовных дел о хулиганстве. М., 1980. С. 45.; Векленко В., Бавсун М. Проблемы толкования оценочных категорий уголовного закона // Уголовное право. 2003. № 3. С. 15—17.; Кострова М.Б. О влиянии языка уголовного закона на эффективность правоприменительной деятельности // Современное состояние российского общества и актуальные проблемы борьбы с правонарушениями: Материалы межвузовской научно-практической конференции (16 ноября 2000 г.). Уфа: Восточный университет, 2002. С. 20; Вознесенская О. Камень в руке хулигана — не всегда оружие // Российская юстиция. 2001. № 6. — С. 51

deviated from general social norms.

Based on the above, we propose understanding "deliberate disrespect for public order" as a significant deviation from the commonly accepted behavioral norms in society that disrupt the normal functioning of the system of social relations, including peace, normal working conditions, citizens' recreation, and peaceful living, as well as the normal operation of institutions, enterprises, and organizations.

Unfortunately, in Paragraph 1 of the decision of the Plenary of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 14, 2002, No. 9, on "Judicial practice in cases of hooliganism," the definition of "deliberate disrespect for public order" includes the category of "gross violation of public order." In our view, it would be beneficial to add the above-proposed concept to this decision.

When explaining hooliganism, the concept of "deliberate disrespect for public order" is closely related to the category of "open disrespect for society," because only by deliberately disregarding public order and openly disrespecting societal norms can the person manifest the objective aspect of hooliganism.

The next issue is how many people should be considered when interpreting open disrespect towards them? Furthermore, this can manifest as disrespect towards society in general, any group of people, or even an individual. For instance, if person E beats person U in public view, this action may not be considered hooliganism because it does not violate the rights of others present.

To properly classify hooliganism, the concept of "open disrespect for society" should be applied uniformly, and we believe it should be clarified in the Plenary's decision mentioned above.

V.Ya. Kozachenko concludes that the public nature of hooliganism is manifested in the commission of such acts in public places. He further emphasizes that hooliganism is an attack on public interests, as the hooligan grossly violates public order and openly disrespects society, thereby directly attacking public interests. If the victim is a physical person and the crime is committed in a place not considered a public space, the offender should be held criminally liable for the crime committed against the individual (property)¹.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the public nature of hooliganism is important for determining the actions of a person that violate public order and openly disrespect society.

¹Козаченко И.Я. Публичность как обязательный признак хулиганства // Проблемы советского уголовного права и криминологии. Свердловск, 1973. С. 116-125.

We cannot fully agree with the position that hooliganism must only be committed in public places because public order can be violated in the presence of many witnesses or even just a few people. In this regard, as N.V. Zhogin rightly pointed out, "the law does not focus on where others can see who is violating public order, but rather on the essence of the actions."¹

In considering the objective aspect of hooliganism under Article 277, Part 2, Item "v", it should be emphasized that hooliganism involves not only the intentional disrespect for public norms of behavior or other actions reflected in Part 1 of the article, but also an additional feature – the demonstration of cold weapons or objects that could cause harm to a person's health (as weapons), threatening to use or actually using them, which is required for criminal liability.

Given the content of the objective aspect of hooliganism outlined in Part 2, Item "v", it is necessary to address the criminal-legal meaning of the concept of "cold weapons or objects that could cause harm to a person's health (as weapons)".

According to Article 3 of the "Law on Weapons," cold weapons are defined as "weapons designed to strike a target with physical force." In addition, items that can be used as cold weapons are defined as professional,

¹ Жогин Н.В. Борьба с хулиганством — дело всех и каждого. М.: Юрид. лит., 1967. С. 28.

industrial, or sports tools or objects designed for use in professional, production, or household activities, or industrially or manually made piercing or cutting tools (knives, daggers, and other pointed, sharp-edged, or cutting items), or items that can cause harm when physical force is applied (baseball bats, softball bats) are also considered as weapons.

According to Part 4 of the Resolution of the Plenary Session of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated June 14, 2002, No. 9¹, "On the practice of handling hooliganism cases," the use of other items that could potentially harm a person's health refers to cases where the accused, during a hooligan act, caused or attempted to cause bodily harm to the victim.

In our view, it is important to note that the act of threatening with a firearm during the commission of a crime is part of the objective element of hooliganism as described in Part 3, Item "v" of the article.

Thus, threatening with non-functional, unusable weapons (such as training weapons) or decorative, souvenir, toy weapons should not be considered as hooliganism. However, it is important to assess how individuals react to the item shown by the offender.

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленумининг 2002 йил 14 июндаги 9-сонли “Безориликка оид ишлар бўйича суд амалиёти ҳақида”ги қарори // <https://lex.uz/docs/1452654>

As V.S. Yegorov pointed out, such objects, by their tactical and technical characteristics, may be recognized as a criminal weapon if they are objectively capable of causing harm to a person's life or health. He suggests considering items like hammers, iron rods, bolts, spears, and similar objects as potential criminal weapons.

Some researchers argue that the concept of "objects specially designed for causing bodily harm" needs to be revisited. The understanding of "objects used as weapons" in this context does not seem appropriate, as it would unnecessarily narrow the definition of hooliganism.

When discussing the use of force in hooligan acts, such as physical assault or threats to use force, we fully agree with L.V. Serdyuk's view¹. He emphasized that physical violence is performed against an individual (or group of individuals) in a way that causes organic,

physiological, or psychological harm, or restricts their freedom of speech or movement through unlawful means².

Referring back to our national legislation, we believe that Article 277, Part 1 of the Criminal Code considers acts of hooliganism that involve beating, inflicting light injuries, or damaging or destroying another person's property as

¹Сердюк Л.В. Насилие: криминологическое и уголовно-правовое исследование. М.: Юрлитинформ, 2002. С. 22.

²Ўша жойда.

having material elements of hooliganism, since the social danger of the consequences caused by these acts is necessary to classify the act as a crime. Similarly, for acts like destroying or damaging property, it is necessary to establish that significant harm was done to the property.

We agree with researcher A.V. Ragulin's view that hooliganism is a mixed (formal and material) crime, as the acts described in different parts of Article 277 have both formal and material elements.

For example, the composition described in Part 1 of Article 277 is considered material, whereas in Part 2, Item "v" (showing cold weapons or objects that could harm a person's health, threatening or using them) and Item "g" (demonstrating gross disrespect for public norms), the crime is considered complete once the individual merely demonstrates or threatens to use a cold weapon or engages in blatant impudence.

Similarly, hooligan acts described in Part 3 of Article 277, involving deliberate violation of public norms, recidivism, or showing a firearm to intimidate or threaten, or when the act is committed during a public event or against a public officer maintaining order, will be considered completed when these actions are carried out.